

Influence of Organizational Culture on Administrative Effectiveness of Secretaries in Public Polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria

Authored by

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Abstract

Administrative effectiveness are crucial aspects of public polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria, that are interrelated and can impact the performance of secretaries. However, this area has been perceived as major challenge, leading to several administrative ineffectiveness. The study, therefore, examined the influence of organizational culture on administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria. The descriptive survey design was adopted, with a sample size of 149 secretaries drawn from public polytechnics in the state. Data were collected using a questionnaire, with reliability tests yielding 0.65 for administrative effectiveness and 0.69 for organizational culture. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. Utilizing a sample of 149 respondents, findings indicate a high level of administrative effectiveness among secretaries, as reflected by a weighted mean score of 3.31, with low variability in responses. The prevalent organizational culture in these polytechnics emphasizes Basic Underlying Assumptions as reflected by average mean of 3.27, surpassing Artefacts (mean = 3.18) and Espoused Values (mean = 3.10). This highlights a strong focus on core beliefs guiding organizational behavior. Regression analysis demonstrates a significant influence of organizational culture ($F = 30.071$, $p < 0.000$) on administrative effectiveness, with specific elements of culture, such as Artefacts and Espoused Values, playing key roles. The study concluded that organizational culture significantly influences secretaries' administrative effectiveness in Oyo State polytechnics. Continuous training and promoting a strong organizational culture were recommended to enhance improve administrative outcomes.

Keywords: *Administrative Effectiveness; Organizational Culture; Public Polytechnics; Oyo State; Secretaries*

Introduction

Effectiveness is the extent to which stated goals and objectives are met. It is a measure of the success in achieving a clearly stated objective (Moye, 2019). Measuring effectiveness can be like taking the pulse of an organization. It involves going beyond surface appearances and delving into the heart of its operations. In the case of secretaries, effectiveness is not just about checking tasks off a list. It is about efficiency, accuracy, and the seamless flow of information.

Administrative effectiveness refers to an administrator's capacity to realize the goals and aims of the organization (Akinyemi and Ajayi, 2020). For an organization to function optimally, it must successfully fulfil its objectives. The more objectives met, the stronger the organization's performance and the more effective is the combined resources (both human and material resources). Hence, there should be a mutual reinforcement of objectives whereby individual and organizational objectives are accomplished together. Administrative effectiveness is the progressive response to administrative efforts and activities with the purpose to achieve stated goal. Administrative effectiveness is about achieving the goals of an organization through the efficient, accurate, and well-organized execution of administrative duties.

Globally, administrative effectiveness is the backbone of organizational success, ensuring that institutions operate efficiently and meet their objectives. It encompasses the ability to plan, organize, lead, and control resources to achieve goals with optimal productivity. In today's interconnected world, administrative effectiveness is influenced by rapidly changing technologies, dynamic workforce diversity, and evolving stakeholder expectations. Effective administration requires adaptability, innovation, and strategic decision-making to address challenges such as resource constraints, misaligned goals, and ineffective communication systems (Panyakham et al., 2021). Despite advancements in management practices and tools, many organizations still face difficulties in integrating these approaches holistically, especially in environments characterized by bureaucratic processes and limited access to modern technologies.

These global challenges are equally evident in institutions of learning, including public polytechnics in Oyo State. Here, administrative effectiveness is critical for providing high-quality education and ensuring institutional efficiency (Adesanya, Sotayo and Bolarinwa, 2020). Secretaries, as central figures in administrative processes, play a vital role in managing communication, coordinating activities, and ensuring adherence to institutional policies. However, their effectiveness is often hindered by challenges specific to the local context. Organizational culture may not always support innovation or professional growth, leaving secretaries undertrained and undervalued. This leads to inefficiencies in record-keeping, communication, and task management. Furthermore, the lack of clearly defined performance metrics and limited investment in capacity building initiatives creates a gap between the expectations of administrative roles and the resources provided, undermining the overall effectiveness of administrative staff in public polytechnics in Oyo State.

Secretaries are administrative professionals who serve as the backbone of organizational operations, ensuring efficiency and coordination in various tasks (Asogwa, and Agusiobo, 2022). They are responsible for duties such as managing schedules, organizing meetings, maintaining records, handling correspondence, and facilitating communication within and outside the organization. Their importance lies in their ability to enhance productivity, ensure smooth workflows, and support executives or departmental heads in decision-making processes. In institutions like public polytechnics, secretaries play a vital role in coordinating academic and administrative activities, maintaining accurate documentation, and fostering effective communication, thereby contributing significantly to the institution's overall success and functionality.

Measuring administrative effectiveness is complex because there is no one-size-fits-all approach. While different perspectives exist, the 3-dimensional theory of administrative effectiveness, originally formulated by William Reddins focuses on balancing task-oriented work styles with relationship orientated ones (Otamiri, 1970). This study adopted these aspects to measure administrative effectiveness among secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria. Task orientation is a work style where efficiency reigns supreme. People with this approach prioritize adhering to established procedures, completing tasks on time and accurately, focusing on achieving goals and meeting deadlines with a structured and results-driven mind set (Ogunode, Olowonefa & Ayoko, 2023).

Organizational culture as a factor that can influence administrative effectiveness of secretaries could be referred to as the shared values, beliefs, norms, attitudes, and behaviours that characterize the work environment and interactions within an organization (Bamidele, 2022). It represents the collective understanding of "how things are done" within the organization and influences the behaviour and decisions of its members (Schein and Schein, 2017). The concept of organizational culture is measured by artefacts, espoused values, and basic underlying assumptions (George, Owoyemi and Onakala, 2012).

Artefacts refer to the visible, tangible aspects of organizational culture, including physical structures, technology, and symbols. These are the concrete manifestations of the organization's values and beliefs, readily observable by members and outsiders alike. Espouse values are the stated official value of the organization. They are the stated beliefs, ideals, philosophies, principles and goals that an organization professes to uphold dearly (Oboreh, 2020). These values are often articulated in mission statements, codes of conduct, and official communications. When these values are emphasized and upheld by the institution's leadership, secretaries are more likely to prioritize tasks that align with these values, such as providing timely and accurate information to students and stakeholders. This alignment fosters a sense of purpose and dedication among secretaries, enhancing their administrative effectiveness. Basic underlying assumptions are often the unconscious beliefs, perceptions, and interpretations that shape organizational culture (Akintola, 2020). Beliefs about the purpose of education, the nature of authority, and the importance of collaboration shape how secretaries perceive their roles and responsibilities within the institution.

Statement of the Problem

Administrative effectiveness ensures efficient resource management and timely decision-making, fostering agility and transparency within the organization. Secretaries play crucial roles in enhancing this operational efficiency and communication by navigating intricate digital platforms, communicate effectively across diverse channels, and manage data in a technology-driven environment. When secretaries are effective, administrative tasks are completed seamlessly and efficiently, leading to increased productivity and reduced operational bottlenecks. However, preliminary investigation and literature review revealed that organizational culture may challenge administrative effectiveness (Shao, Wang and Feng, 2015). If the challenges to the administrative effectiveness of secretaries are not addressed, it could lead to disrupted academic schedules, delayed responses to student inquiries, and errors in financial management, jeopardizing the overall functioning and reputation of the public polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Several studies have investigated factors influencing administrative effectiveness in educational institutions (Adesanya, Sotayo and Bolarinwa, 2020), but there is a notable scarcity of research specifically addressing the influence of organizational culture on the effectiveness of secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria. While studies have explored aspects of organizational culture in other contexts, such as corporate settings, the unique dynamics of public polytechnics in Oyo State warrant further investigation to understand how this variable impacts administrative effectiveness in this specific context. Hence, this study investigated the influence of organizational culture and computer self-efficacy on the administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to investigate the influence of organizational culture on administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State. The objectives were to:

- i. identify the level of administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State Nigeria.
- ii. examine the prevalent organizational culture in public polytechnics in Oyo State;
- iii. determine the influence of organizational culture on administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State;

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the level of administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria?
2. What is the prevalent organizational culture in public polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀1: There will be no significant influence of organizational culture on administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public Polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria

Theoretical Framework

The Three-Dimensional Theory (3-D Theory)

The theory of administrative effectiveness, initially conceived by William Reddins and later developed by Reddins, Landers, and Redins, introduces two primary variables crucial to administrative efficacy: Task Orientation (TO) and Relationship Orientation (RO). The third dimension, termed effectiveness, emerges from the dynamic interaction between these two foundational components (Otamiri, 1970). The Three-Dimensional Theory (3-D Theory) is relevant to the study because it provides a foundational framework for understanding and evaluating administrative effectiveness. By elucidating the interplay between Task Orientation (TO) and Relationship Orientation (RO), the theory offers insights into how administrators balance competing demands to achieve desired outcomes, making it a pertinent lens through which to analyse and assess administrative practices in various organizational contexts.

Schein's Organizational Culture Model

Edgar H. Schein is a renowned organizational psychologist who has made significant contributions to the understanding of organizational culture (Schein and Schein, 2017). Schein's model of organizational culture is based on the premise that organizational culture is a layered phenomenon, with each layer influencing the other. His model consists of three main levels. Among the factors determining organizational culture is artefacts. This is the outermost layer and represents the visible elements of an organization's culture. Artefacts include the physical structures, symbols, language, dress code, technology, and other tangible aspects that are easily observable. The second layer delves deeper into the organization's culture by focusing on its espoused values and beliefs. Espoused values are the stated values and norms that the organization claims to follow. The third layer is basic underlying assumption. Basic Assumptions tuned out its relevancy in determining organizational culture. This is the core and deepest layer of Schein's model. Basic assumptions are the unconscious, taken-for-granted beliefs and values that underlie the organization's behaviour. Schein's model of organizational culture is relevant because it provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the complex layers of organizational culture. This model offers valuable insights for leaders and consultants by highlighting the interconnectedness of these layers and emphasizing the importance of addressing underlying assumptions to effectively diagnose, manage, and transform organizational cultures.

Methods

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. The target population comprised of 149 secretaries working in public polytechnics in Oyo State. This implies that the population covered The Polytechnic Ibadan, Ibadan, Adeseun Ogundoyin Polytechnic, Eruwa and Oke-ogun Polytechnic, Saki. The sample size for the study was 149. Since the population is moderate in size and relatively small, the total enumeration sample size was used in the study. The instrument that was used for data collection in this study was questionnaire. The validity of the questionnaire was ensured through an evaluation by the thesis supervisor and two experts in Information Management for face and content validity. The reliability of the measuring instrument was assessed through a pilot study. The data collected for this study was analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 24. Descriptive statistics was used to answer research question 1 and 2, while, inferential statistics was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the level of Administrative Effectiveness of Secretaries

Level of Administrative Effectiveness	VH	H	L	VL	Mean
Task Orientation					
<i>Administrative tasks are fulfilled efficiently</i>	(76) 51%	(64) 43%	(9) 6%	(0) 0.00%	3.45
<i>I have exceptional skill in carrying out the task assigned</i>	(65) 43.6%	(71) 47.7%	(13) 8.7%	(0) 0.00%	3.35
<i>Tasks are prioritize based on their urgency</i>	(65) 43.6%	(71) 47.7%	(13) 8.7%	(0) 0.00%	3.35
<i>Error-free documents and reports are consistently produced</i>	(61) 40.9%	(75) 50.3%	(13) 8.7%	(0) 0.00%	3.33
<i>My organizational skills contribute to a smooth and efficient office operation.</i>	(33) 22.1%	(71) 77.9%	(13) 8.9%	(0) 0.00%	3.22
Average Mean for Task Orientation					3.34
Relationship Orientation					
<i>Effectively resolve challenge</i>	(25) 16.8%	(111) 74.5%	(6) 4.0%	(7) 4.7%	3.03
<i>Building and maintaining positive relationships with colleagues and superiors</i>	(76) 51%	(64) 43%	(9) 6%	(0) 0.00%	3.45
<i>Interpersonal relationships influence the overall effectiveness</i>	(26) 17.48%	(65) 43.6%	(24) 16.1%	(34) 22.8%	2.56
<i>The communication skills contribute positively to the overall effectiveness of administrative tasks</i>	(60) 40.03%	(66) 44.3%	() 6%	(0) 0.00%	3.45
<i>Seeking feedback to improve task performance</i>	(65) 43.6%	(71) 47.7%	(13) 8.7%	(0) 0.00%	3.35
Average Mean for Relationship orientation					3.17
Overall Effectiveness					
<i>Effectively resolve challenge</i>	(65) 43.6%	(71) 47.7%	(13) 8.7%	(0) 0.00%	3.35
<i>Providing solutions to problems encountered</i>	(65) 43.6%	(71) 47.7%	(13) 8.7%	(0) 0.00%	3.45
<i>Problem-solving abilities significantly contribute to the overall effectiveness</i>	(76) 51%	(64) 43%	(9) 6%	(0) 0.00%	3.45
<i>Training and development enhance overall efficiency</i>	(109) 73.2%	(40) 26.8%	(0) 0.00%	(0) 0.00%	3.72
<i>Effective time management skills influence the overall effectiveness</i>	(71) 47.7%	(65) 43.6%	(13) 8.7%	(0) 0.00%	3.45
Average Mean for Overall Effectiveness					3.43
Weighted Mean for Administrative Effectiveness					3.31

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

Decision rule: 1.00 – 1.49=Very Low, 1.50 – 2.49=Low, 2.50 – 3.49= High, 3.50 – 4.00=Very High

Note: VH= Very High, H=High, L=Low, VL=Very Low.

The analysis of administrative effectiveness among secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State shows generally high performance across task orientation, relationship orientation, and overall effectiveness, with a weighted mean of 3.31. For task orientation, respondents rated their ability to efficiently fulfil tasks the highest (mean: 3.45, 94% positive), while organizational skills had the lowest score in this category (mean: 3.22), indicating a relative gap in this area. Relationship orientation also showed strong performance, particularly in building relationships and communication (mean: 3.45, 94% positive), though interpersonal relationship influence scored the lowest (mean: 2.56), signaling room for improvement. Overall effectiveness was rated highly, with problem-solving and training receiving top scores (mean: 3.45 and 73.2% Very High ratings), though time management, despite being the lowest in this dimension (mean: 3.35), still reflected a high level of competency. The task-related mean (3.34), relationship mean (3.17), and overall effectiveness mean (3.43) highlight consistent strengths across these dimensions. To further enhance performance, efforts should focus on strengthening organizational skills and interpersonal relationship dynamics.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on Prevalent Organizational Culture in the Public Polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria

<i>Prevalent Organization Culture</i>	<i>SA</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Artefacts					
<i>The visible symbols reflect a positive organizational culture</i>	(76) 51%	(64) 43%	(9) 6%	(0) 0.00%	3.45
<i>Artefacts effectively communicate the values and expectations</i>	(26) 17.4	(65) 43.6	(24) 16.1	(34) 22.8%	2.56
<i>Disconnection between organizational artefacts and the administrative work environment</i>	(60) 40.3	(66) 44.3	(18) 12.1	(5) 3.4%	3.21
<i>The visible elements and artefacts contribute to a vibrant administrative atmosphere</i>	(65) 43.6	(71) 47.7	(13) 8.7	(0) 0.00%	3.35
<i>Artefacts play a minimal role in shaping the administrative environment</i>	(62) 41.6	(76) 51.0	(11) 7.4	(0) 0.00%	3.34
Average Mean for Artefacts					3.18
Espoused Values					
<i>The espoused values align with creating a positive and efficient administrative environment</i>	(58) 38.9%	(78) 52.3%	(13) 18.7%	(0) 0.00%	3.30
<i>The stated values effectively guide the behaviour and interactions within the administrative work environment</i>	(34) 22.8%	(115) 77.2%	(0) 0.00%	(0) 0.00%	3.23
<i>Noticeable discrepancy between the espoused values and the actual administrative practices</i>	(26) 17.4%	(110) 73.8%	(6) 4.0%	(7) 4.7%	3.04
<i>The shared values contribute significantly to a sense of purpose and effectiveness in administrative tasks</i>	(69) 46.3%	(71) 47.7%	(26) 17.4%	(35) 23.5%	3.40
<i>Inadequate organizational values that would positively impact administrative effectiveness</i>	(24) 16.1%	(64) 43.0%	(26) 17.4%	(35) 23.5%	2.52
Average Mean for Espoused Values					3.10
Basic Underlying Assumptions					
<i>The fundamental assumptions and beliefs create a positive administrative environment</i>	(65) 43.6%	(71) 47.7%	(13) 8.7%	(0) 0.00%	3.35

<i>Identify and resonate with the core beliefs and assumptions that underlie the organizational culture</i>	(59) 39.6%	(75) 50.3%	(15) 10.1%	(0) 0.00%	3.30
<i>The basic underlying assumptions foster trust and collaboration in shaping the administrative environment</i>	(31) 20.8%	(118) 79.2%	(0) 0.00%	(0) 0.0%	3.21
<i>Disconnection between the fundamental assumptions and the actual administrative work environment</i>	(25) 16.8%	(111) 74.5%	(6) 4.0%	(7) 4.7%	3.03
<i>The basic underlying assumptions contribute minimally to the administrative environment</i>	(76) 51.0%	(64) 43.0%	(9) 6.0%	(0) 0.00%	3.45
Average Mean Basic Underlying Assumptions					3.27
Weighted Mean for Organization Culture					3.18

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

Decision rule: 1.00 – 1.49=Strongly Disagree, 1.50 – 2.49=Disagree, 2.50 – 3.49= Agree, 3.50 – 4.00=Strongly Agree

Note: SD= Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, A=Agree, SA=Strongly Agree

The analysis of organizational culture in public polytechnics in Oyo State reveals a generally positive environment, with a weighted mean score of 3.18. Artefacts, representing visible cultural symbols, scored an average mean of 3.182, with the highest-rated item, reflecting positive organizational culture, scoring 3.45 and supported by 94% of respondents, though some reservations exist about their alignment with organizational values (mean score: 2.56). Espoused values, guiding organizational principles, received a mean score of 3.098, with a high of 3.40 for their contribution to purpose and effectiveness, while discrepancies between stated values and practices scored lower (3.04). Basic underlying assumptions, foundational cultural beliefs, had an average mean of 3.268, with their minimal contribution to the administrative environment rated highly (3.45), though some misalignment with administrative work was noted (3.03). Despite these challenges, artefacts, espoused values, and assumptions are viewed as positive contributors to the organizational culture. Addressing gaps in aligning artefacts and values with administrative practices could further enhance the administrative effectiveness and cultural cohesion in these institutions.

H₀1: There will be no significant influence of organizational culture on administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public Polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria

The null hypothesis one which states that there will be no significant influence of organizational culture on administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public Polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria was tested using multiple linear regression analysis. In the analysis, the values of administrative effectiveness were regressed on the values of organizational culture. The data for organizational culture (independent variable) was generated by summing responses of all variables items respectively while that of administrative effectiveness of secretaries (dependent) was generated by adding responses of all items used to measure the variable. The regression test results are presented in the table below.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.619 ^a	.384	.371	.49586

b. Predictors: (Constant), Basic Underlying Assumptions, Espoused Values, Artefact

Source: Field Survey Result, 2024

Table 4: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.181	3	7.394	30.071	.000 ^b
	Residual	35.652	145	.246		
	Total	57.833	148			

a. Dependent Variable: Administrative Effectiveness

b. Predictors: (Constant), Basic Underlying Assumptions, Espoused Values, Artefact

Source: Field Survey Result, 2024

Table 5: Coefficients

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.880	.295		2.982	.003
	Artefact	.466	.127	.413	3.668	.000
	Espoused Values	.198	.084	.197	2.355	.020
	Basic Underlying Assumptions	.095	.123	.079	.769	.443

a. Dependent Variable: Administrative Effectiveness

Source: Field Survey Result, 2024

The analysis reveals that organizational culture significantly influences the administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H01). Regression results show that 38.4% of the variance in administrative effectiveness is explained by cultural factors, with artefacts and espoused values emerging as the most impactful predictors, while basic underlying assumptions lack significance. Artefacts, representing tangible elements like symbols, have the strongest influence, contributing 0.466 units per unit increase, followed by espoused values, which reflect shared principles and add 0.198 units. The model demonstrates statistical significance, with an F-value of 30.071 and a p-value of 0.000, confirming the predictors' explanatory power. These findings suggest that polytechnics should prioritize visible cultural elements and shared values to enhance secretarial efficiency and organizational success.

Discussion of Findings

According to the data presented in response to the first research question, the level of administrative effectiveness among secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria, based on a sample of 149 respondents, the findings showed average scores for Task Orientation, Relationship Orientation and Overall Effectiveness.

Task Orientation (3.34), indicating that respondents generally perceive high effectiveness in task-related competencies such as administrative efficiency, task prioritization, and organizational skills. This reflects strong performance in task fulfilment, though there is slightly less emphasis on the contribution of organizational skills compared to other areas.

Relationship Orientation (3.17), indicating a generally high level of effectiveness in areas related to relationship orientation, communication, and feedback. This suggests that respondents predominantly rate these competencies positively, with stronger emphasis on building relationships and communication, while interpersonal relationships show relatively lower perceived influence.

Overall Effectiveness (3.43), indicating a consistently high level of perceived overall effectiveness in resolving challenges, problem-solving, and leveraging skills like time management and training. This suggests that respondents generally view these competencies as significant contributors to their overall administrative effectiveness, with minimal low ratings.

The weighted mean across the three measures attached to administrative effectiveness; Task Orientation, Relationship Orientation and Overall Effectiveness, is approximately 3.31. This indicates that the level of administrative effectiveness of Secretaries in the selected institutions is fair enough, particularly with strong performance in problem-solving, task fulfilment, and administrative efficiency. While all areas are rated positively, there is slightly less emphasis on interpersonal relationships and organizational skills compared to other competencies. This however, indicates that, while administrative effectiveness of secretaries is moderately fair in the selected institutions, there is need for improvement.

This finding is relatable and supported by a study conducted on secretaries in the Oyo State Civil Service. The civil service study, which involved 600 secretarial staff and their superiors, employed stratified sampling to assess effectiveness¹. Both studies highlight high performance in administrative roles, with a strong emphasis on task and relationship orientation contributing to overall effectiveness. This consistency across different settings reinforces the perception of secretaries as effective in managing administrative responsibilities within the public sector in Oyo State.

The findings on the administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State is also parallel with a study on factors contributing to effective mobile learning (M-Learning) in universities². Both studies emphasize the significance of self-efficacy and ease of task execution as essential components of effectiveness in their respective contexts. While the polytechnic study highlights task orientation and relationship management as key to administrative success, the M-Learning study underscores similar factors in optimizing educational practices. Together, these studies reinforce the importance of developing individual competencies and creating supportive environments to enhance overall effectiveness across diverse professional and educational settings.

The research question two on the prevalent organization culture in public polytechnics in Oyo State has average score for Artefacts, Espoused values and Basic Underlying Assumption drawn from a sample of 149 respondents on a 1 to 4 scale.

The overall average mean for artefacts stands at 3.182, indicating that while artefacts are generally perceived positively, there are mixed views on their effectiveness and relevance.

The overall average mean for espoused values is 3.098, indicating a generally positive perception, although concerns about discrepancies between stated values and actual practices are evident. The overall average mean for basic underlying assumptions is 3.268, reflecting a generally positive perception, though some respondents express concerns about their actual impact on the administrative environment.

The weighted mean for organizational culture across these three dimensions is 3.18. This suggests that the prevalent organizational culture in public polytechnics in Oyo State, Nigeria is perceived positively by the majority of respondents, with artefacts, espoused values, and basic underlying assumptions contributing to the administrative environment. However, there are notable areas where alignment and effectiveness could be improved to enhance administrative effectiveness. The findings also indicate that organizational culture significantly impacts administrative effectiveness in public polytechnics in Oyo State, particularly through the dimensions of artefacts and espoused values.

This aligns with studies from various contexts, including senior high schools and universities, which emphasize the role of organizational culture in enhancing institutional performance. Both the Oyo State and Batam City studies highlight how specific cultural elements, such as leadership and shared values, influence governance, educational outcomes, and administrative effectiveness, Nabella, et al. (2022). Similarly, literature reviews and empirical studies from Indonesia, Norman, Paramansyah, and Abdan, (2022) and Ethiopia corroborate the importance of organizational culture in fostering institutional success, emphasizing the value of clear ethics, shared values, adaptability, and effective communication. The Ethiopian study further underscores those specific cultural types, such as clan and hierarchy cultures, have varying effects on academic and organizational effectiveness, Gebretsadik, (2022). Collectively, these findings stress the need for cultivating positive and supportive organizational cultures to enhance leadership, administrative performance, and overall institutional success in educational settings.

Conclusion

The study concluded that organizational culture significantly influences the administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State, with basic underlying assumptions and artefacts playing pivotal roles. Strengthening tangible cultural elements and reinforcing core values are essential for enhancing administrative efficiency. These findings underscore the importance of cultivating a supportive and well-defined organizational culture to drive effective administration in educational institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. To enhance the administrative effectiveness of secretaries in public polytechnics in Oyo State, institutions should prioritize the development of organizational and interpersonal skills through targeted training programs. Professional development workshops focused on time management, problem-solving, and digital administrative tools will further improve efficiency. Additionally, fostering a supportive work environment by promoting effective communication, leadership support, innovation, recognition and structured feedback mechanisms will help address existing gaps and enhance workplace relationships.
2. Aligning organizational culture with actual practices is crucial. Institutions should reinforce transparency, ethical administration, and leadership effectiveness by ensuring that espoused values reflect in daily operations. Strengthening cultural artefacts and shared values can enhance institutional identity and governance.

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